

Review article

Memantine: A look ahead. Insights into structure, syntheses, receptor binding mechanisms, drug hybrids and formulations, and potential repurposing

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ABSTRACT

Since its approval for clinical use more than two decades ago, memantine has become a blockbuster drug against Alzheimer's disease (AD). Unlike other FDA approved small molecules for the treatment of AD, essentially acetyl cholinesterase inhibitors, memantine behaves as *N*-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptor antagonist. However, it is a weak and non-specific NMDA receptor channel blocker that has shown to be safe in slowing the decline of moderate to advanced AD symptoms. In fact, those of us familiarized with AD, are aware of clinical protocols where memantine is usually prescribed to mitigate late stages of this neurological disorder, following previous treatment with donepezil and other inhibitors. The role of memantine for either preventing or disrupting amyloid formation, yet promising, remains inconclusive. The pharmacological basis and mode of action of memantine are well known and have been reviewed from different standpoints, often within the context of adamantane scaffolds. In recent times, further analyses combining experiment and computational simulation have disclosed subtle features of memantine-receptor interactions and previously unrecognized mechanistic insights, which are summarized herein. Likewise, there is a growing interest in memantine derivatives, not only against neurodegeneration, but also versus unrelated pathologies. Such studies arising from lab observations and preclinical assessments at most, point to memantine's repurposing and open the door to further explorations and translation. It is noteworthy that some structural aspects of memantine, including crystal packing and polymorphism, are usually overlooked. This review pays attention to such key elements and updates synthetic protocols, including the first preparation of memantine in continuous flow.

1. Introduction

It is unnecessary to underline the clinical and societal impact of Alzheimer's disease (AD) and other forms of dementia, which are characterized by cognitive impairment with progressive and devastating memory loss along with difficulties in communication and physiological function. As the most prevalent neurological disorder, AD will presumably hit over 150 million people by 2050 at a global scale [1,2]. Currently there is no cure for AD, although early detection facilitates therapy, even if the disease can be silent enough for long periods and then leading to abrupt decline. While formation of amyloids (either plaques or fibers) and/or synaptic alteration may be responsible for AD evolution, all therapeutic approaches have found little or limited

success. In recent years, some biopharmaceuticals such as monoclonal antibodies lecanemab and donanemab, have been approved for early symptomatic AD [3], albeit clinical data remain unconvincing.

Palliative actions have focused traditionally on small-molecule inhibitors, a market with increasing demand indeed [4], and particularly acetyl cholinesterase enzyme (AChE) and NMDA receptor inhibition. Representative AChE inhibitors include FDA-approved synthetic donepezil and rivastigmine along with natural product galantamine [5–7], while memantine is an atypical NMDAR inhibitor that also exhibit promiscuous antagonism against AChE and MAO receptors, among others. Its structural simplicity, a lipophilic cyclic hydrocarbon linked to an amino group is likewise amazing. Approved by FDA in 2003 [8], memantine constitutes a salient example of serendipity and repurposing itself from a simpler precursor, amantadine, i.e. memantine devoid of

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List of abbreviations

AChE	acetyl cholinesterase enzyme
AD	Alzheimer's disease
AMPA	α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid
APPs	amyloid precursor proteins
A β	amyloid- β
BACE-1	β -site amyloid precursor protein cleaning enzyme 1
BBB	blood brain barrier
BDNF	brain neurotrophic factor
BuChE	butyrylcholinesterase
CDs	carbon dots
CNQX	6 cyano-7-nitroquinoxaline-2,3-dione
CSP	cortical spread polarization
EDC-HCl	1-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-3-ethylcarbodiimide

	hydrochloride
FAD	familial Alzheimer's disease
FENM	fluoroethylnormemantine
KATP	ATP-sensitive K ⁺
MAO	monoamine oxidase
MCI	membrane-to-channel inhibition
NHS	N-hydroxysuccinimide
MTDL	multi-target directed ligands
NMDA	N-methyl-D-aspartate
NMDAR	N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor
PEG	poly(ethylene glycol)
PLGA	poly(lactide-co-glycolide)
RNS	reactive nitrogen species
ROS	reactive oxygen species
S1R	sigma-1 receptor

methyl groups, which was introduced as antiviral to treat influenza in the 1960s. Memantine should thus be circumscribed to the family of adamantane-containing drugs. Readers are therefore referred to some reviews and reports (to name a few) featuring the history and medicinal chemistry of such substances, with treatments from concise to comprehensive [9–14]. Memantine derivatives, namely hybrids and bioconjugates, have also attracted attention as multitargets agents [12,13,15], with recent prospects beyond neurocognitive disorders [16]. It is true that memantine is currently far from cutting-edge biomedical research portfolios. As mentioned, the drug appears to mitigate cognitive impairment in advanced AD stages, albeit physicians usually encourage to discontinue administration when the illness reaches its highest peak (as we can witness).

As Fig. 1 shows, the interest in memantine has however kept increasing over the past 20 years at a steady-state growth rate according to a SciFinder search. Remarkably, numerous citations, especially from the COVID-19 pandemic onwards, indicate memantine's repurposing to treat so disparate pathologies such as Parkinson's disease, schizophrenia, epilepsy, autism, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and others, either alone or in combination with other drugs. We shall discuss briefly the fundamentals and soundness of such approaches at the end of this article. Probably, everything one wanted to know about memantine is essentially known; so one wonders whether there is need for another review.

The present review extends our current knowledge on the effects of memantine, focused primarily on AD, nevertheless, encompasses new structural and synthetic pursuits, including some analogs, as well as ongoing research on existing mechanisms and novel cellular pathways, and evaluates both challenges and limitations. Surprisingly, some

Fig. 1. Number of publications on memantine (from 2005 to mid-July 2025) according to SciFinder search.

interesting structural aspects remain ignored, which might be leveraged for improved formulations and administration. Likewise, moving memantine's synthesis from batch to continuous in line with greener protocols is a must and should afford simplified and scaled-up designs. The overall discussion is aimed to provide valuable ingredients towards the development of more potent adamantane-based inhibitors, while offering new opportunities for exploring memantine further. Most literature cited covers the past five years to a significant extent, although in hindsight older contributions are quoted as well.

2. Structural features and synthetic updates

2.1. Stereochemistry and polymorphism

Memantine (1, Fig. 2), 3,5-dimethyladamantan-1-amine, is commercially marketed as its hydrochloride (Mem·HCl) and sold in the form of tablets/capsules and oral solution. The small drug fulfils Lipinski's rules in terms of molecular weight and lipophilicity, even if only the amino group accounts for HB-donating interactions. While the free base melts at ~ 153 °C, a broad range of melting points have been reported for the mono-HCl salt (>250 °C in any case), which might simply reflect different degrees of purity and/or the co-existence of polymorphic structures (*vide infra*). Although no biological differences are reported, both structure and solubility differences should affect dosage and PK profiles.

Probably, one of the most interesting aspects, largely overlooked, if not ignored, lies in stereochemistry. Clearly, the molecule has a plane of symmetry, in which the enantiomeric moieties of memantine are reflections of each other. Both the carbon atom attached to the amino function and the tertiary carbon are pseudochiral (or pseudoasymmetric) atoms [17], both being *r*-configured. The configuration of those pseudochiral centers remains unaffected upon mirror reflection. The quaternary carbon atoms exhibit opposite configurations. Thus, despite the presence of four stereogenic centers (*R,S,r,r*), it is unnecessary to use any stereodescriptor for memantine, because no stereoisomers are possible [18]. One could be tempted to describe memantine as a

Fig. 2. Memantine is globally an achiral molecule, despite the presence of stereochemical elements: chiral and pseudochiral carbon atoms.

meso-compound in view of the symmetry plane, yet accompanied by chiral centers. However, it would also be inappropriate since there are no alternative chiral stereoisomers, thus deviating from the standard definition of *meso* substances within a subset of configurationally distinct stereoisomers. In any case, these stereochemical considerations are particularly noticeable, because chiralization and/or desymmetrization of memantine could afford new derivatives with differential pharmacological action. Some memantine-based compounds obtained by synthetic derivatization are inherently chiral, albeit chiral resolutions remain unexplored.

As noted above, the solid-state structure is poorly understood, which is quite surprising for such a key drug. There are at least two polymorphs (denoted Forms I and II) for memantine hydrochloride [19–24], albeit the assignments based largely on PXRD data in patented documents are not completely unambiguous and, in addition, the existence of anhydrous and hydrated forms is not usually specified. Actually, it is uncertain which form is administered in most pharmaceutical formulations. Form I appears to be the most stable polymorph that can be crystallized from ether or ethanol-ether mixtures [19,20,22,24]. Form II has been obtained from other solvent/antisolvent combinations and the two polymorphs can simultaneously occur as well [23]. The second polymorph slowly decomposes above 200 °C, as inferred from DSC analyses, and clearly the hydrochloride melts with decomposition, which casts doubt on a confident melting point for this substance. The latter could be attributed to solvent removal or water removal prior to melting. A third polymorph for Mem·HCl has also been documented (called Form R) with distinctive 2θ peaks, while others are coincidental with those of Form II, and endothermic peaks (DSC analysis) at 202, 279 and 342 °C, at which extensive decomposition has already taken place [25]. Notably, one reliable crystal structure has been reported for a substoichiometric hydrate, namely memantinium chloride 0.1-hydrate [26], having an appealing channel-like arrangement (Fig. 3). The four six-membered rings of the adamantyl skeleton adopt a typical chair conformation, whereas the chloride anion links to the organic cation via N–H···Cl bonding. Disordered water molecules are located along the channels and coordinated with the anions through O–H···Cl bonds. The fact that channels enable the reversible intercalation/desorption of water molecules make the hydrate unsuitable as pharmaceutically acceptable salt.

Numerous crystal structures reported in recent years for memantine salts include among others, benzosulfonate [27], methanesulfonate [28], carboxyborane [29], or carboxylate derivatives [30,31], together

with simple inorganic salts other than chloride [32]. Interestingly, four polymorphs could be successfully screened for a naphthoic acid salt [31] and two forms for memantine-HSO₄ [32]. The latter appears to be a suitable alternative to the hydrochloride salt due to enhanced solubility, non-hygroscopicity, and platelet-like morphology. Decomposition of the high-temperature polymorph was observed above 200 °C as well (reversible crystal-to-crystal transition occurs at ca. 105 °C).

2.2. Synthetic improvements

A recent overview has reported the stepwise syntheses of all FDA-approved inhibitors against AD [33]. The main syntheses of memantine have been summarized previously [10–12], most generally starting from 1,3-dimethyladamantane (**2**) or derivatives such as 1-halo, 1-hydroxy or 1-carboxylic acid 3,5-dimethyladamantane, and involving three or four overall steps. Convenient two-step protocols include the reaction of **2** with either acetonitrile or formamide in a mixture of strong mineral acids for prolonged time, and chromatographic purification is usually required to separate memantine from the reaction mixture [34, 35]. An enhanced procedure for the synthesis of 1-HCl in good overall yield (83%) has been reported, using formamide, instead of acetonitrile, in a Ritter-type reaction in the presence of nitric acid for 2 h only. Acid hydrolysis at reflux for ~1 h results in memantine hydrochloride after cooling (Scheme 1) [36,37]. The process can in addition be feasible for large scale production [38,39]. Some variations have been introduced in the Ritter reaction, such as the use of acetone cyanohydrin to afford the formamide intermediate [40], albeit no particular advantage is noticeable relative to other documented syntheses.

An interesting synthesis of memantine and other aminated derivatives, which include racemic drugs such as rasagiline or sertraline, involves an intermolecular radical C_{sp3}-H amination catalyzed by hypervalent iodine reagents [41]. Alkanes and aryl-substituted alkanes are subjected to regioselective amination with sulfonamides in the presence of I₂ and iodobenzene bis(4-bromobenzoate) as stoichiometric oxidant and photoirradiated with blue (LED) light (Scheme 2).

In a very recent step forward, a continuous-flow synthesis of memantine-HCl has been developed starting from acenaphthene, instead of the usual adamantane skeleton [42]. Individual reactions involve hydrogenation of the acenaphthene core to perhydroacenaphthene, acid-catalyzed skeletal rearrangement of the latter to 1,3-dimethyladamantane, followed by nitration and subsequent reduction of the nitro functionality to an amino group. The batch routes of this lengthy strategy require harsh conditions, especially the aromatic ring hydrogenation of acenaphthene necessitating high pressures and temperatures, or the use of strong Lewis acids for isomerization to adamantane to occur. The authors were able to smooth the overall transformation encompassing the heterogeneous catalyst-packed column flow hydrogenation over DMPSi-Rh/Pt@Al₂O₃ at ambient conditions, a liquid-liquid biphasic flow rearrangement using the ionic liquid [bmim] Cl/AlCl₃, in-line separation of the two phases, connection to a homogeneous flow nitration and further hydrogenation to the desired amino functionality. Memantine can thus be obtained in sufficient purity and 28% overall yield (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Channel-type crystal packing of memantinium chloride 0.1-hydrate. Green atoms denote chloride anions and red spheres water molecules, with the oxygen atom located at a 3-fold rotation axis. Reproduced from Ref. [26] as open access publication. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Scheme 1. Improved two-step protocol to memantine hydrochloride (1-HCl).

Scheme 2. Memantine synthesis by iodine-catalyzed C–H amination under photoirradiation.

3. Biological and molecular mechanisms

3.1. Memantine-receptor interactions: new insights into inhibitory paths

The pharmacological action of memantine as an uncompetitive, voltage-dependent NMDA receptor antagonist is well established, and the effect is usually associated to its therapeutic role as NMDA hyperstimulation appears to be involved in several neurodegenerative pathologies, including AD [8–11,14,43,44]. In short, the heteromeric NMDA receptor, composed of two GluN1 and two GluN2 subunits is activated by the agonist action of glycine and glutamate, thereby opening the receptor and releasing Mg^{2+} blockade. This results in the flow of Ca^{2+} ions into the cell (Fig. 5). Prolonged opening has, however, a detrimental effect due to the excitotoxic damage caused by calcium excess. Thus, the overall effect of memantine is linked to mimicking the voltage-dependent Mg^{2+} blockade of the NMDA receptor, which is reduced during the progression of AD.

Given the weak, uncompetitive NMDA receptor inhibition, the positive effects of memantine on cognitive impairment could also be linked to its molecular promiscuity by either altering or disrupting additional mechanisms involved in neurodegeneration. It is known that memantine is capable of inhibiting to some extent other cholinergic and dopaminergic receptors [45]. Also, it has been invoked that the distinct responses of the NMDA receptor are induced by and at regionalized subunits followed by different downstream signaling paths [46,47]. The accurate mechanism by which the NMDA receptor channel is blocked by memantine and other drugs, which include dizocilpine (MK-801, 5), ketamine (6), phencyclidine (7), neramexane (8) or polycyclic alkylamine RL-208 (9) (Fig. 6) has long been elusive [48,49]. Even if their responses are variable, the lack of functional group complexity suggests

that the pivotal role of these hydrocarbon cages, bearing no more than azabicyclo or amino-alkyl moieties, should be governed by a subtle balance between lipophilicity and non-covalent H-bonding interactions. A rationale was provided by the crystal diffraction analysis of MK-801 complexed with a modified receptor (by removing the N-terminal domains from the GluN1-GluN2B receptor sites), which enabled to map the binding site [50]. The crystal structure together with molecular dynamics (MD) simulations reveal that memantine and MK-801 bind within the vestibule of the ion channel in a similar fashion. While MK-801 binds in two poses, only one was detected for memantine. Both antagonists enter and bind to the pore cavity regardless of the voltage, although an applied voltage drives the blockers deeper into the channel, where they form H-bonding with an asparagine nitrogen atom (N613 of Glu-N2B). The off-rate of memantine is ~ 100 -fold faster than that of

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the NMDA receptor showing the voltage-dependent Mg^{2+} blockade. Release of this function allows key ions to move from extracellular to intracellular media and viceversa along with the exogenous blockade exerted by memantine and other antagonists. Adapted and modified from Ref. [8].

Fig. 4. Continuous-flow synthesis of memantine involving four steps from acenaphthene. Modified and reproduced from Ref. [42]. Open access article under the Creative Commons Attribution Non-Commercial License.

Fig. 6. Antagonists, other than memantine, of the NMDA receptor.

MK-801, which explains the enhanced efficiency of the former accompanied by voltage-dependence upon binding.

Interestingly, high-resolution structures (2.5–3.5 Å) using single-particle electron cryo-microscopy, supported by MD simulations as well, of the interaction of phencyclidine, (*S*)-(+)-ketamine, and memantine at the binding site in GluN1-2B NMDA receptor regions have also been reported [51]. Interactions with the pore residues occur to different extent for the three inhibitors, even if all share the same binding domain (Fig. 7), where they control primarily the speed of off-responses, but not on-responses. Remarkably, further molecular details have been disentangled by electron cryo-microscopy capturing the substructure of GluN1-GluN2B NMDA receptor in its open state and bound to an allosteric modulator as well [52]. Opening results in a notable tension in the GluN2B ligand-binding domain loop. The process forces to rotate and bend the pore-forming helices in GluN1 and GluN2B domains, thereby modifying the bislobular arrangement of the pore to an overall twofold

symmetry.

Memantine could not only block voltage-dependent open channels, but also acid-sensing ion channels, whose interaction shifts desensitization to more acidic pH values [53]. This transit should be feasible because memantine is a weak acid ($pK_a = 10.4$, corresponding to dissociation of conjugate ammonium salt) in equilibrium between ionized (protonated) and non-protonated (uncharged) forms. The ionized/charged form will be able to interact through strong electrostatic contacts with lipid headgroups at the outer part of the membrane, while uncharged memantine is highly hydrophobic and should be residing within the membrane.

The long-held tenet that NMDA receptor blockers can access the binding site only when the channel is open has been challenged in recent studies. Actually, memantine was found to bind in the absence of agonist and at different voltages, which point to a second site occupation, rather superficial to the channel, and accessible when the receptor is closed [54]. Competitive assays, however, ruled out inhibition by occupation of memantine at the second site. Memantine could either slowly dissociate and move to the extracellular medium or pass to the deep site, thus blocking the channel. The argument has remained speculative until assessment by further electrophysiological experiments [55], which account for a dual inhibitory mechanism as the blockers can penetrate the channel through two distinctive pathways, i.e. the well-established hydrophilic route from the extracellular solution to the open channel gate, and a least-known hydrophobic path from plasma membrane to the channel. The latter, termed membrane-to-channel inhibition (MCI), involves membrane fenestration (Fig. 8). Thus, at physiological pH memantine will exist predominantly in its charged (protonated) form. The fraction of uncharged memantine in aqueous solution will be scarce, whereas this form will be prevalent at the second “reservoir” site in the membrane. An increase in extracellular pH will concomitantly increase the fraction of uncharged memantine both in solution and the

Fig. 7. Structural analyses of agonist-bound GluN1a-2B NMDA receptors. (a) Cryo-EM density of the agonist-bound rat GluN1a and GluN2B in magenta and dark green, respectively. (b) EM density of bound glycine (left) and glutamate (right) at GluN1a and GluN2B, respectively. (c) Zoomed views of the channel blocker binding cavity. The binding site has three layers, namely Thr-ring (GluN1a-Thr648 GluN2B-Thr647) at the channel gate, the hydrophobic ring (GluN1a-Val644 and -Ala645 and GluN2B-Leu643 and -Ala644), and the Asn-ring (GluN1a-Asn616 and GluN2B-Asn615). Reproduced partly from Ref. [51]; HHS public access publication. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Pathways showing incorporation of memantine into the deep channel of NMDA receptor. (a) Conventional mechanism. Top: charged memantine from the extracellular medium cannot access the deep site when the channel is closed; bottom: charged memantine transits to the deep site through the channel when the agonists (A) bind, thus opening the channel gate. (b) Membrane-to-channel inhibition (MCI). Top: neutral (uncharged) memantine present in the membrane is unable to access the deep site unless membrane to channel fenestration takes place; bottom: the uncharged species, however, can access the deep site through membrane-gated fenestration after the agonists bind. Reproduced from Ref. [55] (open access by Creative Commons License).

membrane, thereby favoring MCI that enables transport to the deep site. This mechanism could be general and work for other channel blockers, so long as protonated and unprotonated species are available depending on the extracellular pH. The authors tested the hypothesis by preparing the corresponding trimethylmemantinium cation (*N,N,N*-3,5-pentamethyladamantan-1-ammonium iodide). As a permanently charged derivative, MCI does not occur as the ionized drug cannot transit from the membrane to the deep site.

The fact that neurological mechanisms are usually mediated by electric signaling provides the basis to target other voltage-based receptors. As inferred from studies with mice, the ATP-sensitive K^+ (KATP) channel Kir6.2 may be potentially relevant to cognitive/memory improvements. This voltage-dependent channel along with the Kir6.1 channel are inhibited by memantine. Their blockade also contributes to reduce the elevated extracellular Ca^{2+} concentrations [56]. Furthermore, a very recent study indicates that memantine can decrease calcium influx by selectively inhibiting other ionotropic glutamate receptors such as calcium-permeable AMPA (α -amino-3-hydroxy-5-methyl-4-isoxazolepropionic acid) subtype [57]. The AMPA receptors are also composed of four subunits (GluA1, GluA2, GluA3 and GluA4), assembled as either homomeric or heterodimeric complexes, which are associated with auxiliary transmembrane regulatory proteins (γ) that stabilize the open state of the receptor. By focusing on homomeric GluA2 under various conditions, data suggest that memantine inhibition required the presence of such auxiliary subunits, with IC_{50} values for GluA2 in the presence of $\gamma 2$ and $\gamma 8$ of $49 \pm 2 \mu M$ and $48 \pm 3 \mu M$, respectively.

Cellular damage mechanisms that can potentially be reversed by memantine are rooted in electric polarization as well. Among them cortical spread polarization (CSP) inhibition seems to be sound enough

and paves the way to alternative therapies. CSP involves a sharp depolarization of neurons and glia cells within the cerebral cortex because of brain injuries. Accordingly, CSP represents a potential biomarker that can be monitored through negative direct current shift in electrocorticographic waves, which also induces a microvascular response. By exploring the effects of NMDA receptor antagonists, such as ketamine and memantine, on electrically triggered CSP in healthy and brain-injured rats, memantine improved neurovascular function in sham and brain-injured animals. In addition, memantine prevented neurological impairment in preclinical and randomized traumatic brain injury trial [58].

3.2. Amyloidosis inhibition

In line with the underlying prion principle, i.e. aggregation of misfolded proteins as the origin of neuropathogenicity [59], it has been reported through numerous dose-dependent assays, including animal models, that memantine reduces the production of amyloid- β ($A\beta$) peptide precursors [60]. It is unclear, however, if memantine modulates and/or attenuates protein trafficking or rather disrupts the formation of $A\beta$ aggregates and hence plaque deposition. The latter would suggest an intercalating role that disaggregates preformed $A\beta(1-42)$ fibrils. In fact, the less bulky, but structurally similar, amantadine (devoid of methyl substituents), did not affect $A\beta$ accumulation at the same concentrations [61]. Further studies have confirmed that amyloid peptides can actually coordinate with drugs currently employed against AD, which include both memantine and other acetylcholinesterase enzyme (AChE) inhibitors (Fig. 9), irrespective of peptide concentrations [62]. Higher binding capacity were observed for donepezil (10) or tacrine (11) than that for memantine or galantamine (12). Computational docking and

comparison with experimentally resolved drug-enzyme complexes indicate that binding to an amyloidogenic core mimics the interaction of such drugs to their targets, which are primarily guided by π - π stacking, cation- π interactions, and hydrogen bonding. For comparative purposes, interactions involving galantamine as typical AChE inhibitor and memantine as pore channel blocker, as displayed in Fig. 10.

The central bicyclic moiety of galantamine is wrapped by the amino acids of the YFTGAIIGNFY peptide sequence (Fig. 10a), while the core interacts with the binding groove in the other FYTGAIIGNFY sequence (Fig. 10b). In both complexes, the AChE inhibitor forms rich π - π and cation- π interactions with the designed amino acids. With the first peptide, galantamine also forms a H-bond with the OH group of a tyrosine residue through its charged amino group (seven-membered ring) in nearly half of the top 10 chosen structures, and through its OH group (lower ring attached to a chiral center, Fig. 9) in 3 of the top 10 selected structures. In the FYTGAIIGNFY-drug complex, galantamine forms the same H-bonding with tyrosine through the charged amino (3 out of 10) and OH (2 out of 10) groups as well. Memantine, having a more “spherical” structure, is wrapped by both peptides, which cluster around the adamantane core (Fig. 10c and d). Relative to tacrine (with similar conformational rigidity), memantine is not as tightly wrapped, which can be attributed to the bulkier skeleton of the alkylated adamantane. As expected, memantine complexes with both peptides through rich π - π and cation- π interactions with the designed amino acids. Moreover, the amino group forms H-bonds with the OH group of tyrosines in nearly half of the top 10 chosen structures for each peptide.

The action of memantine on cerebral amyloid angiopathy, characterized by the presence of A β deposits, has also been evaluated in APP23 transgenic mice. By measuring the amount of soluble and insoluble A β 40 and A β 42 fractions, together with the levels of APPs (amyloid precursor proteins), APP-processing enzymes (i.e. α -, β -, and γ -secretases), and A β -degrading enzymes (insulin-degrading enzyme expression), memantine appears to enhance the latter in particular, relative to control assays. Overall, this results in a significant reduction of cerebrovascular A β plaques [63]. Likewise, *in vitro* effects of the (+)-MK-801 (dizocilpine) enantiomer, with respect to the action of memantine, on A β 40 and A β 42 peptides, have been evaluated through thioflavin T fluorescence assays [64]. Both drugs are capable of accelerating the formation of a β -sheet structure, albeit faster with (+)-MK-801. This acceleration is accompanied by a decrease in the fluorescence signal, which was not observed in the absence of ligand. Results indicate that MK-801 induces a progressive decrease in the monomeric form of soluble peptides, which do not

bind to the drug, nevertheless (as inferred from NMR data). Accordingly, both memantine and dizocilpine appear to speed up the transition of A β peptides to insoluble forms, which gave rise to negative ThT assays.

Subsequent studies have proven that formation of A β peptides and impairment of Ca²⁺ homeostasis are in fact interlocked. Although misfolded oligomers do not interact directly with NMDA and other receptors (e.g. AMPA to a lesser extent), they can induce mechanical activation of the lipid bilayer, thus causing compression and stretching sensed by the receptor itself [65]. The cellular stress induced by oligomers and calcium-mediated toxicity was evaluated by monitoring the change of intracellular Ca²⁺ concentrations in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells (Fig. 11). The treatment of such cells with Zn-stabilized A β peptides led to an increase of intracellular Ca²⁺ levels. Addition of NMDA and AMPA receptor antagonists (memantine and CNQX, 6 cyano-7-nitroquinoxaline-2,3-dione, respectively), slowed down the influx of Ca²⁺. The genuine mechanical effect could further be corroborated by means of lipids, which cause membrane tension as well. Thus, whereas lysophosphatidylcholine neutralizes the activation of the NMDA receptor induced by the oligomers, arachidonic acid produces the same activation as the oligomers without additive effects. These observations are consistent with the implication of amyloid oligomers in the abnormal transit of extracellular Ca²⁺, which can be counterbalanced by ion channel agonists. In context, other exogenous factors can trigger similar effects. It has been reported that viral infections alter glutamate biosynthesis and receptor activation, which includes the NMDA receptor, results in aberrant influxes of glutamate and hence, dysregulation of Ca²⁺ flux. Viral infection is thus followed by deficient neurotransmission and potential neurodegeneration [66].

4. Memantine (bio)conjugates and analogs: quest for improvement

In general, preclinical and clinical data, before and after memantine's approval, evidence that adamantanes, including amantadine, memantine, and their analogs, exhibit low to moderate affinity and poor therapeutic indexes in disease models targeting CNS disorders [10,12,14,67]. A plethora of pharmacological studies reported in recent times often involve either the co-administration of various inhibitors or hybrid synthetic combinations affording heterodimers in the search for dual or synergistic effects (*vide infra*). From a structural viewpoint, most derivatives involve linking memantine to other inhibitors as well as (bio) conjugation with synthetic or naturally-occurring substances, in the hope of ameliorating cognitive decline. From a conceptual standpoint, the approach lies in the use of multi-target directed ligands (MTDL), given the multifactorial nature of AD. Rather than the conventional one target-one molecule paradigm, MTDL focuses on designing molecules acting on multiple targets and pathogenesis mechanisms [68]. Collectively, all such analogs could be denoted as “memantine hybrids”, which have been recently discussed in an outstanding short review [15]. Certainly and for proper semantics, the term “hybrids” may still engender some ambiguity. For instance, it is unclear whether one deals with chemically-modified ligands, i.e. covalently-linked heterodimers, or a physical formulation of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs) plus other additives and supports to enhance drug delivery. Such combinations can likewise include the formation of ionic salts or co-crystals. For the sake of clarity, we will first concentrate on pharmaceutical formulations involving two or more inhibitors clinically employed against AD, moving then to covalent (bio)conjugates that combine memantine with AChE inhibitors along with synthetic and natural products.

4.1. Combined memantine formulations

Interest in combining memantine with AChE inhibitors has continued at a fast pace, as they target concurrently cholinergic and glutamatergic receptors. Thus, cognitive decline is ameliorated with galantamine-memantine co-administration, which was found to be

Fig. 9. Structures of FDA-approved acetylcholinesterase enzyme (AChE) inhibitors: donepezil (10), tacrine (11), galantamine (12), and rivastigmine (13). The use of tacrine has been discontinued due to adverse side effects.

Fig. 10. Molecular graphics showing the binding modes of galantamine and memantine to designed peptides YFTGAIIGNFY and FYTGAIIGNFY. (a) Computational docking of galantamine bound to the first peptide, designed and validated against (e) a materialphore obtained from PDB ID 4EY6 (complex with human AChE). (b) Computational docking of galantamine to the second peptide, designed and validated against (f) materialphore from PDB ID 4EY6. (c) Computational docking of memantine bound to the first peptide, validated against (g) a materialphore obtained from PDB ID 4TWD (ion channel ELIC captured in a pore blocker bound conformation by memantine). (d) Computational docking of memantine to the second peptide, validated against (h) materialphore extracted from PDB ID 4TWD. The backbone of peptides and specific amino acid-drug binding motifs are shown in blue, while the interacting amino acid side chains are represented in black/licorice. H-bonds involving tyrosines and drugs are shown by black dotted lines. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [62]. Copyright by the American Chemical Society. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Intracellular free Ca^{2+} levels in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells incubated with Zn-stabilized $\text{A}\beta_{40}$ and $\text{A}\beta_{42}$ oligomers, before and after the inhibition of AMPA and NMDA receptors by CNQX and memantine, respectively (A and C bar graphics). Plots B and D show the fluorescence values over time. Reproduced from Ref. [65] (open access article under a CC-BY License).

superior to the combined use of donepezil and memantine, or galantamine alone. The combination appears to act simultaneously on the $\alpha 7nCh$ receptor subunit and NMDA receptor, counterbalancing other cellular pathways associated with the progression of AD, such as the formation of kynurenic acid metabolites, BDNF (brain neurotrophic factor), and oxidative stress. Cognitive responses declined when the use of galantamine was discontinued [69]. The positive effect observed when memantine is combined with an AChE inhibitor has also been attributed to reducing the oxidative DNA damage and increase the glutathione redox ratio (GSH/GSSG), both mechanisms occurring in AD patients with respect to a control group. The result is not conclusive, nevertheless, as similar levels of oxidized DNA precursors are present in patients treated with either inhibitor alone [70]. When considering donepezil, usually employed alone in early diagnosis, beneficial effects have been reported for long-term treatments in combination with memantine [71]. Meta-analyses of drug validation in randomized, placebo-controlled trials, point to credible efficacy and safety of the combined therapy only in patients with moderate or severe AD [72].

Additional innovations in the search of memantine's controlled or slow release include encapsulation into polymeric nanoparticles and polymer-stabilized nanoemulsions, suitable for administering memantine (alone or combined) by transdermal or intranasal routes [73–78]. The latter has proven to be convenient for some CNS-acting drugs which may be orally inefficient. Actually, numerous *in vitro* studies show high release and nearly quantitative cell viability. A triple-drug therapy involving donepezil and memantine plus silencing BACE-1 (β -site amyloid precursor protein cleaning enzyme 1), which controls the production of A β plaques, has likewise been developed for nasal delivery [79].

While memantine-loaded nanoparticles have demonstrated little or scarce apparent cytotoxicity based on *in vitro* or *ex vivo* analyses, which can sustain one-dose release for up to 24 h [80], oral formulations achieving prolonged gastric retention would be more suitable for clinical practice. An oral formulation that could enable once weekly administration, potentially applicable to other water-soluble drugs, involves a gastro-retentive dosage capsule, which after dissolution in the stomach unfolds into a stellate structure. The latter composed of polymer-coated memantine blended with a polycaprolactone matrix gradually disintegrates while drug elutes slowly from the stellate arms [81]. Memantine-loaded poly(lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA) nanoparticles, generated by double emulsion technique, followed by surface coating with another non-ionic surfactant, such as poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) have attracted significant attention for memantine delivery as well [82,83]. Studies on brain cell lines indicate that such nanoparticles are non-cytotoxic. In addition, *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies showed that they penetrate across the BBB and evaluation on male mice targeting APP/PS1 and C57BL/6 evidenced a substantial decrease in memory impairment with respect to memantine. Further histological analyses confirmed the reduction of inflammation associated to amyloid formation [82].

Memantine formulations incorporating metal nanoparticles are appealing as well, given their potentiality as imaging theranostics agents, and where the use of polymer matrices has not only a stabilizing effect but also facilitates BBB penetration. The use of metal traces invariably adds a risky ingredient, albeit an example aimed at imaging A β plaques-fibrils involves a memantine nanoemulsion incorporating zinc ferrite NPs encapsulating fluorescein-labeled memantine, plus a micellar nanocarrier [84].

4.2. Memantine hetero-(bio)conjugates

The synthetic modification of memantine, especially the amino group, is easy to achieve and efforts paid to develop and check such analogs through *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are worthwhile. Thus, N-alkylation of memantine allows the preparation of N-trisubstituted and N-alkylated ammonium salts containing long alkyl chains, which exhibit some antagonism towards the NMDA receptor [85]. By harnessing the

nucleophilicity of the amino functionality, covalent heterodimers combining memantine (or amantadine) with an AChE inhibitor can be obtained in a few steps and have largely been documented. Most cases adhere to the aforementioned MTDL principle, with some derivatives shown in Fig. 12.

Heterodimers of 7-methoxyacrine and adamantylamine linked through a hydrocarbon spacer of variable length along with an ureido (or thioureido) tether, exhibit antagonistic activity for both muscarinic and nicotinic-type receptors, thus lacking cholinergic selectivity, and also suppress A β amyloid fibril formation by interfering with BACE1 (β -secretase) [86]. The most effective inhibitors of A β fibrillization were compounds **14g** and **15e-g** having long methylene spacers ($IC_{50-A\beta}$ ~40 nM), and membrane permeation assay predicted for compound **15d** ($n = 5$, $X = O$) a high probability to cross the BBB. Notably, compound **14d** ($n = 5$, $X = S$) gave rise to a similar response to that of memantine against the GluN1a-GluN2B NMDA receptor.

Galantamine-memantine hybrids endowed with rigid structures, i.e. fewer rotatable bonds and/or unsaturated linkers appear to exhibit a higher brain exposure. Compounds such as **16** and **17** could be generated in a six-step synthesis from N-desmethyl galantamine and memantine [87]. Taking galantamine as reference, the four-carbon homologation afforded **16** with moderate efficacy as human AChE inhibitor ($IC_{50} = 1.13 \mu M$), two times more potent than galantamine. Compounds **17** and **18**, which can be regarded as vinyllogous surrogates, exhibited improved inhibition against the same enzyme, being **17** more potent than **16** (ten-fold more, $IC_{50} = 0.115 \mu M$). Regarding NMDA receptor antagonism, compounds **16** and **17** showed comparable inhibition against excitotoxic GluN1/2B response ($IC_{50} = 1.45$ and $1.32 \mu M$, respectively) with a higher selectivity (~11-fold) GluN1/2B over GluN1/2A for compound **17**. In contrast, the alkynyl derivative **18** showed a poorer performance. Docking analyses were in addition performed to assess the influence of the linker on the binding mode. To that end, simulations were conducted on a model structure of AChE based on the co-crystallized complex with donepezil (Fig. 13). Results indicated that compounds **16–18** adopted a binding pose similar to the one accommodated by donepezil. Actually, galantamine-memantine hybrids **16** and **17** established, from a qualitative viewpoint, identical interactions with the hydrophobic pocket. The galantamine unit interacts with Trp86 (indole ring) and forms H-bonds with the side chains of Glu202 and Ser203, whereas the adamantane substructure also established a hydrophobic contact with Trp286. The enhanced activity of **17** could be attributed to the orientation of the alkenyl linker forcing to establish tighter interactions of the nitrogen atoms (at galantamine and memantine units, respectively) with the side chain of Asp74, which are weaker in **16** owing to the flexibility of the saturated spacer.

It is worth mentioning that galantamine-memantine hybrid **16** has also been tested for noninvasive transdermal delivery under constant-current anodal iontophoresis. Based on *in vivo* studies conducted in male rats, the strategy achieved a high delivery efficiency (nearly 78%) of such a memantine derivative into the brain [88].

On the other hand, polyamine-memantine hybrids show significant antagonist activity as NMDA channel blockers, as inferred from studies using recombinant NMDA receptors expressed in oocytes with a voltage clamped at -70 mV [89]. This represented an extension to previous analysis from the same group accounting for the potent antagonism at NR1/NR2A or NR1/NR2B receptor subtypes showed by heterocycle-substituted spermines, compared to memantine itself [90]. Some polyamines incorporating the memantine core through covalent linking are depicted in Fig. 14 which, like memantine, were isolated as HCl or TFA salts [89]. Structure-activity correlations suggest that double hydrocarbon spacers between amino groups are beneficial for enhanced potency, thereby highlighting the importance of an isosteric methylene-amino replacement, along with the presence of a terminal guanidino group. Although not explicitly disclosed through molecular simulations, the presence of basic nitrogen atoms should contribute to multiple binding interactions, despite the greater conformational

Fig. 12. Covalent heterodimers linking memantine and AChE inhibitors.

Fig. 13. Predicted binding arrangements for compounds 16 (A) (carbon atoms in orange) and 17 (B) (carbon atoms in green) at the binding site of AChE. The conformation adopted by donepezil in the complex crystallized with protein are shown for reference (carbon atoms in green). Reproduced from Ref. [87] (open-access publication under Creative Commons License). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

flexibility provided by a long alkyl chain. Compound 23, having the diamino-guanidino spacer scored high against GluN1/GluN2A, GluN1/GluN2B ($IC_{50} = 379.0 \pm 28.8$; 432.7 ± 65.2 nM) with respect to memantine ($IC_{50} = 1376.1 \pm 180.2$; 2099.0 ± 283.9 nM, respectively).

A salient example of multiple hybridization with a focus on MTDL design is provided by conjugation of amantadine, rather than memantine, to fragments of three inhibitors, namely (*S*)-rivastigmine, tacrine (targeting cholinergic and NMDA receptors), and rasagiline (MAO inhibitor), leading to so-called M30D scaffold [91]. Compounds 24 featuring a variable hydrocarbon spacer between the triple core and the adamantyl moiety (Fig. 15) were unable to inhibit AChE, but most of them showed high selectivity as butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) inhibitors. Hybrids with 6, 7, 9, and 12 methylene groups in the linker (24d-g) had the best potency and selectivity towards BuChE, and

particularly compounds 24d and 24e elicited significant neuroprotection by reducing the detrimental effects induced by glutamate. Regarding mechanistic analysis, docking studies support likewise the interactions of 24e in the blockade of NMDA channel pore. In a related approach, oligomeric conjugates consisting of memantine, tacrine, and an *N*-(3-aminopropyl)cinnamide have shown activity as AChE inhibitors (IC_{50} in the range of 13-44 μ M), which was superior to that of tacrine (IC_{50} in the range of 13-44 μ M), even if the latter is no longer prescribed for AD [92]. In any case, conjugation appears to play a decisive role for enhancing drug delivery and ameliorating *in vitro* inhibition.

Memantine Schiff bases constitute another family of analogs that can be simply accessed by direct condensation of memantine with aryl aldehydes, such as salicylaldehyde, 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde, and pyridoxal [93]. The resulting derivatives show increased lipophilicity

Fig. 14. Representative NMDA blockers consisting of polyamine-memantine hybrids.

Fig. 15. Fragment-based design of bioactive amantadine-M30D hybrids looking for neuroprotective effects.

relative to memantine, in terms of log *P* or log *D* partition coefficients. In principle, such derivatives are attractive because imine formation is a reversible transformation and the parent memantine could be released by hydrolysis at acidic pH. Accordingly, the study claims the potentiality of Schiff bases as prodrugs for controlled transdermal application.

Reactions of memantine with pamoic acid (a 2-naphthoic dicarboxylic acid derivative) lead to insoluble salts, for which four polymorphic structures have been reported after crystal screening [94]. Such salts, which should obviously correspond to a global 2:1 memantine:diacid stoichiometry (25), are packed in different arrangements in the unit cell. Thus, Form I comprises two memantinium cations and one pamoate anion, while Form II involves eight cations and four anions, all interconnected through extensive H-bond networks. Memantine pamoates are less soluble and exhibit lower release rates than memantine, which could however be exploited for a sustained release of the drug. Interestingly, each polymorph exhibits reversible mechanochromic luminescence and, in addition, has a distinctive fluorescence emission that could be employed for real-time monitoring of memantine delivery (Fig. 16). The observed luminescence varies from orange to yellow depending on the wavelength blue-shifted to 550, 551, and 549 nm for Forms I, II, and IV, respectively. The authors attributed the blue shift in the emission spectra after grinding to disruption of weak intermolecular bonding by mechanical abrasion. As mentioned earlier (Sect. 2.1), memantine salts other than the usual hydrochloride might be more suitable for drug delivery, but their viability and cytotoxicity should be carefully examined.

Covalent conjugation of memantine to non-metal particles can be exemplified by the amidation reaction with carbon dots (CDs), either

carbon nitride or black carbon, in the hope of affording non-toxic and biocompatible drug formulations [95]. By means of well-known conjugation reactions, carboxylic acid-functionalized CDs were subjected to the linear sequence shown in Scheme 3 where EDC-HCl (a carbodiimide derivative) and NHS (*N*-hydroxysuccinimide) served as coupling agents. The corresponding intermediates (26 and 27) were labile substances, while subsequent reaction with memantine led to a stable amide linkage and memantine-loaded CDs (28) could be isolated after dialysis and freeze-drying. The resulting nanosized material (<5 nm) ensured a good BBB penetration as confirmed on a zebrafish *in vivo* model. Tau aggregation inhibition experiments using the thioflavin-T assay demonstrated that memantine-modified black CDs as well as black CDs alone, were efficient disrupters of aggregation having IC₅₀ values of 1.5 ± 0.3 and 1.6 ± 1.5 µg/mL, respectively. This and related approaches suggest that drug-loaded nanocarriers may be potential nanomedicines for brain diseases [96].

Bioconjugation of memantine with natural ligands constitutes arguably a valuable strategy, aimed at improving drug administration and delivery with little or no side effects. The rationale lies in the fact that neat natural products, and even plant extracts from traditional medicine, exert positive effects against cognitive decline in AD [97]. In such cases, however, the precise molecular mechanisms remain uncertain. On the other hand, memantine hybrids generated by coupling with fragments of enzyme inhibitors other than those targeting cholinergic receptors, show promising activity in different MTDL therapies [98]. This is portrayed, for instance, by memantine-histone deacetylase inhibitor hybrids targeting glioblastoma [99].

In line with these pursuits, conjugation of memantine to naturally-

Fig. 16. Salts (up to four polymorphs) can be obtained by reaction of memantine with pamoic acid. The image shows photographs of memantinium pamoate polymorphs (Forms I-IV) revealing a writing-erasing process under UV light at 365 nm. Reproduced and adapted with permission from Ref. [94]. Copyright American Chemical Society.

Scheme 3. Covalent amidation conducted in buffer solution of memantine and carbon dots.

occurring substances is illustrated by reactions with triptolide (**29**, [Scheme 4](#)), the latter being a polycyclic triepoxide capable of crossing the BBB, yet having limited solubility and non-innocent toxicity.

Conjugation to memantine through a carbamate linkage yielding **33** showed neuroprotection *versus* $\text{A}\beta_{1-42}$ oligomer toxicity in primary cortical neurons, together with inhibition against LPS-induced TNF- α and BV2 cells at nanomolar concentrations [100]. SAR studies have disclosed a series of interesting features, particularly the hydroxyl group at C14 in **29** and its configuration (β -OH) play a key role in biological activity. Thus, compounds **30** and **31**, obtained by oxidation and fluorine-exchange, respectively, exhibited no neuroprotection against amyloid-induced cytotoxicity. The memantine bioconjugate (**33**) involving a carbamate linker without altering the chirality at C14, and generated via previous formation of **32**, had a neuroprotective effect similar to that of parent triptolide; whereas **34**, conjugated with *tert*-butylamine and used as control, lacked the effect and showed peripheral

toxicity as well.

The combination of memantine with natural antioxidants appears to be a sound approach to check the inter-relations, if any, among NMDA receptor inhibition, free-radical capture, and β -amyloid disruption. In this context, ferulic acid (**35**), which is known to protect from $\text{A}\beta$ -neurotoxicity and cellular death, usually associated to the inhibition of ROS (reactive oxygen species) production, has been conjugated to memantine [101]. The insertion of memantine pharmacophores into the covalent hybrid was accomplished by reaction at either a methine bridge or the amino group and involved drug homologation in both cases. To obtain the first derivatives, Boc-monoprotected diamines reacted with **35** yielding the elongated intermediates **36–38**. Boc-deprotection under acid conditions led to **39–41**, which were further coupled to memantine carboxylic acid (**42**), the latter obtained by a Ritter-type reaction. The final amidation step required prolonged reaction under mild conditions in the presence of EDC-HOBt as coupling agents to produce **43–45**

Scheme 4. Derivatization reactions of triptolide, including conjugation with memantine.

(Scheme 5).

N-Derivatization was conducted by reacting first memantine (1·HCl) with Boc-aminosylates. The alkylation products (46–49) were subjected to deprotection of the carbamate moiety and the resulting derivatives (50–53) coupled with 35 to generate memantine-ferulic acid hybrids 54–57 (Scheme 6). Notably, compound 57 behaved as a voltage-dependent NMDA receptor antagonist ($IC_{50} = 6.9 \mu\text{M}$). Furthermore, 57 showed antioxidant properties related to the activation of the Nrf-2 pathway in SH-SY5Y cells. It is pertinent to note that, within such a μM range, neither memantine nor ferulic acid derivatives devoid of the adamantane nucleus, showed effect on A β precursor protein (APP), thus evidencing the importance of bioconjugated analogs.

A few amino acid conjugates, such as H-4-fluoro-phenylalanine-memantine or H-tyrosine-memantine, showed *in vitro* neuroprotective effects against Cu-triggered amyloid toxicity and glutamate-induced excitotoxicity, equivalent to those observed for memantine [102]. Likewise, a short library merging memantine with amino acids, short peptides, and other nootropics known to ameliorate cognitive deficits, has been reported [103]. In all cases, a stable amide bond links the memantine fragment to sarcosine (58), dimethylglycine (59), glycylglycine (60), glycyl-glycylglycine (61), modafinil (62), piracetam (63), and picamilon (64) (Fig. 17), which improved cell viability against glutamate-based neurotoxicity in SH-SY5Y cells. Neuroprotection equivalent to that of memantine could be obtained for 60 and 63, whereas a greater activity accompanied by low cytotoxicity was observed for amino acids, namely sarcosine and dimethylglycine. From a structural viewpoint, ligands 58–64 are all achiral compounds without stereogenicity elements.

Additional memantine and adamantane hybrids have been documented with varied activity and selectivity against NMDA, AChE or BuChE receptors [12,15]. Even if potency and/or PK profiles are adequate, the use of some ligands should be taken with caution, such as tacrine derivatives whose use, as already indicated, has been discontinued in AD treatments. It is worth mentioning analogs where memantine is appended to bulky groups and/or H-donor fragments capable of establishing further hydrophobic and polar interactions with receptors (Fig. 18). The tetrahydrocarbazole derivative 65 was found to be a weaker NMDA receptor antagonist ($IC_{50} = 14.3 \pm 9.1 \mu\text{M}$) than memantine ($IC_{50} = 1.37 \pm 0.08 \mu\text{M}$) through competitive assays [104]. Conjugation with sulfur-containing natural antioxidants, namely glutathione (GSH) or (R)- α -lipoic acid renders memantine hybrids 66 and 67, respectively [105]. The latter behaves as NMDA receptor antagonist and shows in addition a significant inhibition (~40% at 50 μM) against A β (1-42) aggregation, accompanied by antioxidant activity as tested in GL15 cell lines.

Scheme 5. Synthesis of memantine-ferulic acid hybrids functionalized at the adamantane cage. Reaction conditions: (a) EDC, HOBT, TEA, DMF, $N_2(g)$, 12 h, 0°C to rt, (b) HCl 4 M in dioxane, CH_2Cl_2 , 90 min, 0°C to rt, (c) EDC, HOBT, DMF, $N_2(g)$, 36 h, 0°C to rt.

Ad hoc designs of dual-function inhibitors targeting two binding sites are rare, nevertheless. In a very recent study, both memantine and donepezil were modified by a side scaffold of 2-methoxy-4-benzothiazolylphenol, which inhibits A β aggregation [106]. The resulting derivatives, Mem-Benz (68) and Done-Benz (69) would thus have A β -targeting functionality in addition to NMDA and AChE inhibition (Fig. 19). For Done-Benz (69) the observed IC_{50} value and docking score indicated a lower affinity to the enzyme than donepezil, a fact that prevents further investigation as potential therapeutic agent relative to the parent drug.

In stark contrast, the interactions of Mem-Benz (68) with NMDA receptor and A β_{42} fibrils showed promising data, despite the low micromolar affinity for the latter. Thus, Mem-Benz could enter the brains of 5xFAD mice and accumulate in amyloid-rich zones as confirmed by post-mortem analyses of the brains of mice injected with 68. Interestingly, Mem-Benz was inactive as NMDA receptor inhibitor, but released *in vivo* memantine and a benzothiazole metabolite, thereby evidencing its role as prodrug even if a large fraction of 68 remains intact in mice brains. Docking simulations illuminated further this rationale because memantine and Mem-Benz interact with the NMDA receptor at different locations (Fig. 20); the former with the known binding pocket, whereas 68 prefers to bind with the hydrophobic portal (α -helices) of the protein.

4.3. Small memantyl-substituted analogs

A series of compounds bearing the memantyl (3,5-dimethyladamantyl) core have also been introduced in recent years. Biological evaluation and preclinical assays foresee promising developments against neurological decline and beyond. In context, fluoroethylnormemantine (FENM, 70) constitutes a valuable candidate indeed (Fig. 21). Actually, FENM does not derive from memantine; it is an amantadine analog, marketed as hydrochloride as well, where the adamantane hydrocarbon bears a 2-fluoroethyl side chain. Its lipophilicity is comparable to that of memantine, although the fluorine atom is appealing for *in vivo* biomarker labeling. Behavioral assays conducted on male Wistar rats showed a series of pluses relative to memantine, by reducing learned fear without altering locomotion or exploratory abilities, and attenuating despair levels [107]. This study evidences antidepressant properties as well, albeit the authors caution about the generality of such responses, which were not tested in female animals. In a subsequent study, FENM exhibited a synergistic effect in combination with a sigma-1 receptor (S1R) agonist in a mouse model of AD [108]. S1R agonists (e.g. igmesine, cutamesine or PRE-084) are often administered in clinical trials of neurodegenerative disorders, usually

Scheme 6. Synthesis of memantine-ferulic acid analogs functionalized at the amino group. Reaction conditions: (a) K_2CO_3 , KI, DMF, 1 h, 140°C (MW heating), (b) HCl 4 M in dioxane, CH_2Cl_2 , 20 min, 0°C to rt, (c) EDC, HOBT, TEA, DMF, $\text{N}_2(\text{g})$, 12 h, 0°C to rt.

Fig. 17. Structures of synthetic hybrids combining memantine with amino acids, dipeptides, and cognitive enhancers (in brackets, EC_{50} values of the protective effects on APPsw cells).

Fig. 18. Memantine hybrids derived from tetrahydrocarbazole fragment (65) and sulfur antioxidants: GSH (66) and (*R*)-configured lipoic acid (67) (in brackets, IC_{50} value of the NMDA receptor antagonist activity for 65 and antioxidant activity associated to the capacity to inhibit $\text{A}\beta(1-42)$ aggregation for 66 and 67).

associated with antidepressant effects. The combined therapy of FENM and S1R agonist led to synergistic protection against $\text{A}\beta_{25-35}$ -induced learning deficits for both short- and long-term memory responses, whereas a similar combined therapy with memantine achieved short-term response only. FENM alone had comparable effects, during daily administration, to those obtained by memantine, in a mouse model of AD, decreasing amyloid-induced neuroinflammation and oxidative stress [109].

Benzohomoadamantanes are close structurally analogs of memantine, which have found limited success as NMDA receptor channel blockers, nevertheless. A notable exception is compound 71 showing an antagonist effect ($\text{IC}_{50} = 1.93 \pm 0.21 \mu\text{M}$) similar to that of memantine ($\text{IC}_{50} = 1.5 \pm 0.1 \mu\text{M}$), as inferred from *in vivo* studies in *C. elegans* [110].

It is worth mentioning that another memantine analog, DABMA (72 , Fig. 21), featuring a bromomethoxybenzyl substituent at the amino group, is a potent, broad-spectrum antimicrobial agent targeting host endolysosomal pathways, and not evaluated for neuroprotection [111].

Memantine isothiocyanate (73), where the amino functionality is replaced by the $\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{S}$ heterocumulenic linkage, actually proved to be a memantine prodrug that releases H_2S through a cysteine-mediated mechanism and concomitantly generates memantine itself (Fig. 22) [112]. Overall effects observed include the fall of ROS production and reduction in $\text{A}\beta_{1-42}$ self-aggregation in both human neurons and rat microglia cells. Compound 73 can be directly accessed from memantine using thiophosgene at room temperature. In the absence of L-Cys the generation of H_2S is essentially negligible, either using 73 or another

Fig. 19. Structures of chemically-modified memantane and donepezil bearing an amyloid-targeting fragment.

reference H_2S donor. Moreover, like memantane, **73** appears to regulate

cellular homeostasis (autophagy), largely ascribed here to the role of H_2S as signaling modulator in mammalian CNS. The binding activity on the NMDA receptor was assessed in terms of the displacement of [^3H] MK-801 (dizocilpine) in cortex membranes. While memantine exhibits a significant displacement of radioligand both in presence and absence of L-Cys ($K_i = 954.8 \pm 74.2 \text{ nM}$ and $328.8 \pm 10.9 \text{ nM}$, respectively), isothiocyanate **73** showed a significant activity only in the presence of L-Cys as H_2S donor ($K_i = 458.4 \pm 77.7 \text{ nM}$). This result is consistent with a prodrug role, thus suggesting that L-Cys is involved in regulating the affinity of **73** for NMDA receptor (Fig. 22).

Memantine nitrates are structurally simple, polar analogs of memantine. By preserving the amino-adamantanyl skeleton, these substances with dual functionality are expected to exhibit neuroprotection and vasodilation, by inhibiting the NMDA receptor while releasing nitric oxide. Such effects have been reported for a few compounds (Fig. 23) containing one or two nitrate groups (**74–76**), which constitute in addition homologous derivatives of memantine. *In vitro* studies involving mononitrate **74** confirmed enhanced cortical neuroprotection by reducing Ca^{2+} influx [113]. Subsequent studies on memantine nitrates (such as **75**) shed light into their influence on signaling pathways.

Fig. 20. Docking images of NMDA receptor (human GluN1-GluN2, protein structure obtained from that co-crystallized with ketamine, PDB: 7EU7). (a) Magnified views of each ligand's interactions with arrows pointing to location of compounds within the receptor. (b) Ligand interactions with labeled residues within 4 Å-resolution. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [106]. Copyright American Chemical Society.

Fig. 21. Memantyl analogs with diverse biological activity.

Fig. 22. Displacement of [³H]MK-801 binding in rat cortex membranes in the absence or presence of L-cysteine. The acronym memit corresponds to memantine isothiocyanate (73). Image reproduced from Ref. [112]; open access publication under Creative Commons License.

Thus, protective effects, based on assays in rat cultured cerebellar granule neurons, point to concomitant inhibition of ERK pathway and activation of PI3K/Akt pathway, which would account for concentration-dependent protection against glutamate-induced neurotoxicity. Vasodilation occurs via activation of NO (nitric oxide)-cGMP pathway as inferred from *ex vivo* analysis. PK data also indicate that memantine nitrates can cross the BBB, thus reaching quickly brain and other organs [114]. Such nitrates, and even nitrones, may also be beneficial against glioblastoma, by suppressing tumor growth and angiogenesis through delivery of NO around NMDA receptors [115].

There seems to be a cumulative effect arising from the simultaneous release of memantine and NO, which affect the voltage-dependent blockade and regulation of Ca²⁺ influx levels. Fig. 24 illustrates the potential mechanisms whereby Ca²⁺ signaling contributes to NO production in neurodegenerative pathogenesis, AD or Parkinson's disease (PD). Hyperactivation of NMDA receptor not only induces excessive flux of Ca²⁺ ions, but also activation of neuronal NO synthase. In AD soluble A β peptides can likewise facilitate NO generation. It is noteworthy that environmental toxins like pesticides can trigger NO production caused by mitochondrial dysfunction. Moreover, both reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (ROS/RNS) are produced in response to amyloids and pesticides [116]. The use of memantine nitrate results in enhanced neuroprotective effect relative to memantine in animal models, even at lower concentrations. The reaction of NO with thiol groups of Cys residues of the NMDA receptor (in particular at the external domain of the NR2A subunit) inhibits, at least partially, receptor activity via S-nitrosylation reaction, while still benefitting from the voltage-dependent

Fig. 23. Representative memantine nitrates evaluated in concentration-dependent protection against glutamate-induced neurotoxicity (in brackets, protective effects against glutamate induced neurotoxicity).

Fig. 24. Possible pathways in which Ca²⁺ signaling favors NO production in neurodegenerative disorders (AD or PD). Channel blockers such as memantine and memantine nitrate (NO-releasing memantine) can regulate overproduction of NO and excessive Ca²⁺ influx to restore their physiological levels. Reproduced from Ref. [116] (NIH public access article).

blocking of memantine.

Overall, even though SAR studies have not been reported for all functionalized memantine analogs, Fig. 25 showcases a landscape of structural motifs present in the aforementioned examples. Variations in either functional groups or hydrocarbon linkers modulate different effects accounting for cognitive neuroprotection and enhancement.

5. Memantine repurposing and outlook

The well-known therapeutic effects of memantine are linked to its established targets, i.e. NMDA and cholinergic receptors, along with 5-HT₃ and D₂ dopaminergic receptors, and other voltage-dependent and ligand-gated ion channels. The observed interactions account for the clinical effectiveness of memantine to maintain learning and cognition. A recent and comprehensive study outlining the current status and potential applications to pathologies beyond AD, is highly recommended [16]. Early clinical trials after memantine's approval (up to 2009) already unveiled potentiality in non-dementia diseases [117]. The off-target use of memantine in disparate disorders such as schizophrenia, autism, anxiety, depression, alcohol abuse, tobacco and opioid dependence, manias, etc, has grown progressively in recent years. Literature citations claiming memantine's repurposing, alone or in combined therapies, to treat a broad spectrum of pathologies are countless. Unfortunately, in-depth understanding of the mechanistic basis is often missed. In any case, some repurposes involving memantine or small analogs could be mentioned in the present context, such as psychiatric disorders, namely schizophrenia and depression [118], sickle cell disease [119], glaucoma [120], or testicular dysfunction [121]. Conversely, the promising effect of memantine in patients with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) suggesting slow disease progression seems to be unsound [122].

Probably, new opportunities for memantine and other promiscuous inhibitors will come from the enormous variability encountered in cognitive disorders. It appears now evident that the enormous

Fig. 25. SAR analysis of the most promising memantine bioconjugates included in this work.

heterogeneity in symptoms and pathogenesis, more or less related to AD in global terms, make it impossible to continue referring to AD as a single disease [123]. The fact that processes such as inflammation, immunopathic or vasculopathic mechanisms, or cellular signaling, among others, experience progressive and deep changes, evidence the coexistence of numerous molecular mechanisms in AD. While combined therapies, often involving cholinergic or NMDA receptors inhibition,

and/or MTDL strategies should be useful resources in future drug discovery/innovation agendas, further efforts in immunotherapy targeting aberrant A β oligomers [124], along with identification of molecular deficits or hidden pathways that sustain neurodegeneration [125], will be critical for success as unraveled by recent findings. Above all, open science initiatives that share massive genomic and proteomic data will increase the probability of developing efficient drugs [126]. Thus, recent

proteomics data link gene variant *APOE4* to inflammation associated with Alzheimer's, Parkinson's, and other brain diseases [127].

6. Conclusions

Memantine is far from being classified as a magic bullet, although clinical data, at least in prolonged treatments, witness more pluses than minuses. The weak antagonism exhibited by memantine toward NMDA receptor represents its Achilles' heel, although the modular capability of this structurally simple hydrocarbon with minimal functionalization to interact with multiple targets, provides the basis for constructive lead modifications. In recent years, biological analyses, crystallographic studies, and molecular simulations have interrogated with accuracy the mode of action. As salient points, memantine appears to bind, relative to other voltage-dependent blockers such as MK-801, in only one pose within the vestibule of the ion channel with faster off-rates (up to 100-fold). By virtue of its weak acidity as Brønsted acid, memantine may interact with acid-sensing ion channels as well, thus facilitating the pH-dependent residence of protonated and unprotonated forms within the membrane and at the outer part. It is likewise relevant to note the dual inhibitory mechanisms exerted by memantine, and other channel blockers, penetrating the open channel from the extracellular medium, but also through fenestration through membrane-to-channel inhibition. Other peripheral mechanisms, which may improve neurovascular function, appear to be associated with cortical spread polarization inhibition. As mentioned, the action of memantine on amyloid disruption is not conclusive, albeit bioassays and MD simulations unveil the binding of memantine with peptide fragments involving π - π and π -cation interactions along with expected H-bonding with polar amino acid residues.

Although memantine hydrochloride can easily be obtained in a few steps, the first in-flow synthesis reported recently paves the way to cleaner, safer and more efficient production of this drug and its analogs. Hybrid structures encompass conjugation with other AChE inhibitors through rigid and flexible spacers and/or memantine homologation, as portrayed in Figs. 12, 14, and 15 illustrating some structure-activity correlations. Derivatization with polyamines unveils the significant activity of a memantine analog bearing a diamino-guanidino spacer (23) that reinforces hydrophobic and polar contacts. Bioconjugation with natural polycycles and phenolic oxidants (Schemes 4–6) leverages the potential benefits of such substances, as exemplified by compound 57 acting as voltage-dependent NMDA receptor antagonist with antioxidant properties. Synthetic hybrids of memantine with amino acids and peptides (Fig. 17) have resulted in cognitive enhancers. Structurally simple functionalization of the memantyl nucleus, as shown by benzohomoadamantane (71) or nitrate derivatives (74–76) leads to bioactive substances with either affinity or inhibition values matching that of memantine or slightly superior, still within a rather modest μ M range. Memantine repurposing will require conversion into more potent and selective antagonists for the NMDA receptor and others. In summary, the present overview provides new structural insights into solid-state forms, improved synthetic procedures, receptor binding, bioconjugates, and offers, hopefully, valuable guidance for future structure-based designs of memantine analogs. For some of us, memantine has been a useful companion for long time.

Dedication

This article is dedicated in lovely memory to the mother of one of us (P.C.), who succumbed to AD after a long and progressive illness.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

R. Fernando Martínez: Investigation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **María Sánchez-Gallardo:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Pedro Cintas:**

Conceptualization, Investigation, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] P. Scheltens, K. Blennow, M.M.B. Breteler, B. de Strooper, G.B. Frisoni, S. Salloway, W.M. Van der Flier, Alzheimer's disease, *Lancet* 388 (10043) (2016) 505–517, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736\(15\)01124-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0140-6736(15)01124-1).
- [2] S. Long, C. Benoit, W. Weidner, *World Alzheimer Report 2023: Reducing Dementia Risk: Never Too Early, Never Too Late*, Alzheimer's Disease International, London, England, 2023.
- [3] A. Mullard, FDA approvals, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 23 (2023) 88–95, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41573-024-00001-x>.
- [4] L. Howes, Is this a golden age of small-molecule drug discovery? *Chem. Eng. News* 101 (36) (2023) 28–32.
- [5] W.V. Graham, A. Bonito-Oliva, T.P. Sakmar, Update on Alzheimer's disease therapy and prevention strategies, *Annu. Rev. Med.* 68 (2017) 413–430, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-med-042915-103753>.
- [6] I.L.J.T. Brewster, S. Dell'Acqua, D.Q. Thach, J.L. Sessler, Classics in chemical neuroscience: donepezil, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 10 (2019) 155–167, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.8b00517>.
- [7] Y. Zhou, Y. Fu, W. Yin, J. Li, W. Wang, F. Bai, S. Xu, Q. Gong, T. Peng, Y. Hong, D. Zhang, D. Zhang, Q. Liu, Y. Xu, H.E. Xu, H. Zhang, H. Jiang, H. Liu, Kinetics-driven drug design strategy for next-generation acetylcholinesterase inhibitors to clinical candidate, *J. Med. Chem.* 64 (2021) 1844–1855, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.0c01863>.
- [8] A. Witt, N. Macdonald, P. Kirkpatrick, Memantine hydrochloride, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 3 (2004) 109–110, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrd1411>.
- [9] J. Liu, D. Obando, V. Liao, T. Lifa, R. Codd, The many faces of the adamantyl group in drug design, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 46 (2011) 1949–1963, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2011.01.047>.
- [10] L. Wanka, K. Iqbal, P.R. Schreiner, The lipophilic bullet hits the targets: medicinal chemistry of adamantane derivatives, *Chem. Rev.* 113 (2013) 3516–3604, <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr100264t>.
- [11] S. Alam, K.S. Lingenfelter, A.M. Bender, C.W. Lindsley, Classics in chemical neuroscience: memantine, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 8 (2017) 1823–1829, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.7b00270>.
- [12] G. Marotta, F. Basagni, M. Rosini, A. Minarini, Memantine derivatives as multitarget agents in Alzheimer's disease, *Molecules* 25 (2020) 4005, <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules25174005>.
- [13] V. Kumar, V. Kumar, N. Kumar, V. Kumar, K. Jangid, Memantine-based derivatives: synthesis and their biological evaluation, in: A. Sharma, G.P. Modi (Eds.), *Natural Product-based Synthetic Drug Molecules in Alzheimer's Disease*, Springer, Singapore, 2023, pp. 185–209.
- [14] C. Dane, A.P. Montgomery, M. Kassiou, The adamantane scaffold: beyond a lipophilic moiety, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 291 (2025) 117592, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2025.117592>.
- [15] Y.P. Singh, H. Kumar, Recent advances in medicinal chemistry of memantine against Alzheimer's disease, *Chem. Biol. Drug Des.* 104 (2024) e14638, <https://doi.org/10.1111/cbdd.14638>.
- [16] P.K. Tari, C.G. Parsons, G.L. Collingridge, G. Rammes, Memantine: updating a rare success story in pro-cognitive therapeutics, *Neuropharmacology* 244 (2024) 109737, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2023.109737>.
- [17] E.L. Eliel, S.H. Wilen, *Stereochemistry of Organic Compounds*, vol. 67, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1994, p. 1204.
- [18] K.-H. Hellwich, C.D. Siebert, *Stereochemistry Workbook*, Springer, Berlin, 2006, p. 166.

- [19] J. Mills, E. Krumkalns, Adamantyl Secondary Amines. Patent US 3391142 A, 1968.
- [20] A. Scherm, D.P. Hammersbach, Drugs or Medicines for Influencing the Central Nervous System, 1978. Patent US 4122193 A.
- [21] B.A. Punju, P. Nagarajan, K. Srinivasu, T. Rajamannar, Crystal Form II of Memantine Hydrochloride, 2005. Patent WO2005/069742.
- [22] V. Merli, S. Mantovani, P. Daverio, S. Bianchi, A. Spreafico, Process for the Preparation of 1-amino-3,5-dimethyladamantane Hydrochloride, 2006. Patent WO2006/076562 A1.
- [23] V. Merli, P. Daverio, A. Kovacsne-Mezsei, J. Aron-Hime, Polymorphs of Memantine Hydrochloride. Patent WO2006/076560 A1, 2006.
- [24] J. Tihí, M. Meleh, F. Vrečer, R. Zupet, J. Pucelj, M. Pelko, Process for the Preparation of Memantine and its Hydrochloric Acid Salt Form, 2008. Patent EP 1908748 A1.
- [25] IP.COM Prior Art Database 000159896, Novel polymorphic form of memantine hydrochloride, process for preparation and pharmaceutical compositions thereof, Available at: <https://priorart.ip.com/IPCOM/000159896>, 2007.
- [26] W.-J. Lou, X.-R. Hu, J.-M. Gu, Memantinium chloride 0.1-hydrate, Acta Crystallogr. E65 (2009) o2191, <https://doi.org/10.1107/s1600536809031791>.
- [27] V.V. Tkachev, N.S. Tkacheva, V.P. Kazachenko, Structure of 3,5-dimethyl-1-adamantanamine-2,4,6-trisopropylbenzoesulphonate salt in the crystal, J. Struct. Chem. 58 (2017) 615–617, <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0022476617030271>.
- [28] M. Tuksar, M. Rubcic, E. Mestrovic, (3,5-Dimethyladamantan-1-yl)ammonium methanesulfonate (memantinium mesylate): synthesis, structure and solid-state properties, Acta Crystallogr. E Crystallogr. Commun. E75 (2019) 1274–1279, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989019009988>.
- [29] T.I. Ayudhya, A.L. Rheingold, N.N. Dingra, Crystal structure of memantine-carboxyborane, Acta Crystallogr. E75 (2019) 543–546, <https://doi.org/10.1107/S2056989019004092>.
- [30] V. Bhardwaj, M. Shaiwale, B. Lakhani, A. Ballabh, A series of memantine based salts with various aromatic and aliphatic carboxylic acids: crystallographic analysis, Hirshfeld surfaces and dissolution study, J. Mol. Struct. 1206 (2020) 127672, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2019.127672>.
- [31] W. Kuang, J. Liu, X. Lin, S. Wu, J. Gong, Q. Yin, J. Wang, Insoluble salt of memantine with a unique fluorescence phenomenon, Mol. Pharm. 19 (2022) 1389–1399, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.1c00931>.
- [32] M. Tuksar, E. Topic, M. Rubcic, E. Mestrovic, Exploring salts of memantine with inorganic anions: from polymorphism and solid-state transitions to potential for drug formulations, Mol. Pharm. 21 (2024) 4700–4707, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.4c00670>.
- [33] A. Rani, J. Khan, L. Choudhary, M. Kumar, A. Jha, G. Pandey, B. Nand, Unraveling the synthesis and therapeutic potential of FDA-approved Alzheimer's drugs: a comprehensive review, Tetrahedron 175 (2025) 134517, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tet.2025.134517>.
- [34] P.R. Schreiner, L. Wanka, Aminoadamantan-derivate, verfahren zur ihrer herstellung und ihre verwendung, 2006. Patent WO2006010362 A1.
- [35] L. Wanka, C. Cabrele, M. Vanejews, P.R. Schreiner, γ -Aminoadamantanecarboxylic acids through direct C-H bond amidations, Eur. J. Org. Chem. (2007) 1474–1490, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejoc.200600975>.
- [36] B.D. Vu, N.M.H. Ba, V.H. Pham, D.C. Phan, Simple two-step procedure for the synthesis of memantine hydrochloride from 1,3-dimethyladamantane, ACS Omega 5 (2020) 16085–16088, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.0c01589> (Correction: ACS Omega 2020, 5, 26295).
- [37] B.D. Vu, N.M.H. Ba, H.V. Tran, D.C. Phan, An improved synthesis of memantine hydrochloride, Org. Prep. Proced. Int. 52 (2020) 463–467, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00304948.2020.1785807>.
- [38] T.H.T. Nguyen, T.D. Nguyen, D.C. Phan, B.D. Vu, A concise two-step method for preparation of memantine hydrochloride from 1,3-dimethyladamantane, Int. J. Pharma Sci. Res. 12 (2021) 6370–6383, [https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.12\(12\).6370-83](https://doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.12(12).6370-83).
- [39] T.H.T. Nguyen, V.D. Le, S.T. Ngo, T.H.T. Nguyen, D.C. Phan, B.D. Vu, Two step cost-saving process for industrial scale production of 1-amino-3,5-dimethyladamantane hydrochloride (an anti-Alzheimer's drug), Asian J. Chem. 34 (2022) 251–255, <https://doi.org/10.14233/ajchem.2022.23447>.
- [40] E.A. Ivleva, Y.N. Klimochkin, Convenient synthesis of memantine hydrochloride, Org. Prep. Proced. Int. 49 (2017) 155–162, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00304948.2017.1291004>.
- [41] A.E. Bosnidou, K. Muñiz, Intermolecular radical C_{sp^3} -H amination under iodine catalysis, Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. 58 (2019) 7485–7489, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201901673>.
- [42] M. Iwata, Y. Furiya, H. Ishitani, S. Kobayashi, Development of continuous-flow reactions for the synthesis of anti-Alzheimer drug memantine, Chem. Eur. J. 31 (2025) e202403562, <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.202403562>.
- [43] O. Von Bohlen und Halbach, R. Dermietzel, Neurotransmitters and neuromodulators, in: Handbook of Receptors and Biological Effects, second ed., Wiley-VCH, New York, 2006, p. 107.
- [44] J.W. Johnson, S.E. Kotermanski, Mechanism of action of memantine, Curr. Opin. Pharmacol. 6 (2006) 61–67, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coph.2005.09.007>.
- [45] C.G. Parsons, W. Danysz, G. Rammes, Pharmacodynamics of memantine: an update, Curr. Neuropharmacol. 6 (2008) 55–78, <https://doi.org/10.2174/157015908783769671>.
- [46] P. Paoletti, C. Bellone, Q. Zhou, NMDA receptor subunit diversity: impact on receptor properties, synaptic plasticity and disease, Nat. Rev. Neurosci. 14 (2013) 383–400, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3504>.
- [47] R. Wang, P.H. Reddy, Role of glutamate and NMDA receptors in Alzheimer's disease, J. Alzheimers Dis. 57 (2017) 1041–1048, <https://doi.org/10.3233/JAD-160763>.
- [48] W. Danysz, C.G. Parsons, A. Jirgensons, V. Kausz, J. Tillner, Amino-alkyl-cyclohexanes as a novel class of uncompetitive NMDA receptor antagonists, Curr. Pharm. Des. 8 (2002) 835–843, <https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612024607117>.
- [49] J. Compagny-Aleman, A.L. Turcu, A. Bellver-Sanchis, M.I. Loza, J.M. Brea, A. M. Canudas, R. Leiva, S. Vázquez, M. Pallàs, C. Griñán-Ferré, A novel NMDA receptor antagonist protects against cognitive decline presented by senescent mice, Pharmaceuticals 12 (2020) 284, <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics12030284>.
- [50] X. Song, M.O. Jensen, V. Jogini, R.A. Stein, C.-H. Lee, H.S. Mchaourab, D.E. Shaw, E. Gouaux, Mechanism of NMDA receptor channel block by MK-801 and memantine, Nature 556 (2018) 515–519, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-018-0039-9>.
- [51] T.-H. Chou, M. Epstein, K. Michalski, E. Fine, P.C. Biggin, H. Furukawa, Structural insights into binding of therapeutic channel blockers in NMDA receptors, Nat. Struct. Mol. Biol. 29 (2022) 507–518, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41594-022-00772-0>.
- [52] T.-H. Chou, M. Epstein, R.G. Fritzscheier, N.S. Akins, S. Paladugu, E.Z. Ullman, D. C. Liotta, S.F. Traynelis, H. Furukawa, Molecular mechanism of ligand gating and opening of NMDA receptor, Nature 632 (2024) 209–217, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07742-0>.
- [53] V.Y. Shteinikov, T.B. Tikhonova, V.S. Korkosh, D.B. Tikhonov, Potentiation and block of ASIC1a by memantine, Cell. Mol. Neurobiol. 38 (2018) 869–881, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10571-017-0561-6>.
- [54] N.G. Glasgow, M.R. Wilcox, J.W. Johnson, Effects of Mg^{2+} recovery of NMDA receptors from inhibition by memantine and ketamine reveal properties of a second site, Neuropharmacology 137 (2018) 344–358, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2018.05.017>.
- [55] M.R. Wilcox, A. Nigam, N.G. Glasgow, C. Narangoda, M.B. Phillips, D.S. Patel, S. Mesbahi-Vasey, A.L. Turcu, S. Vazquez, M.G. Kurnikova, J.W. Johnson, Inhibition of NMDA receptors through a membrane-to-channel path, Nat. Commun. 13 (2022) 4114, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-31817-z>.
- [56] S. Moriguchi, T. Ishikuza, Y. Yahuki, N. Shioda, Y. Sasaki, H. Tagashira, H. Yawo, J.Z. Yeh, H. Sakagami, T. Narahashi, K. Fukunaga, Blockade of the K_{ATP} channel Kir6.2 by memantine represents a novel mechanism relevant to Alzheimer's disease therapy, Mol. Psychiatr. 23 (2018) 211–221, <https://doi.org/10.1038/mp.2016.187>.
- [57] E. Carrillo, A.M. Romero, C.U. Gonzalez, A.L. Turcu, S. Vázquez, E.C. Twomey, V. Jayaraman, Memantine inhibits calcium permeable AMPA receptors, Nat. Commun. 16 (2025) 5576, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-025-60543-5>.
- [58] M.A. MacLean, J.H. Muradov, R. Greene, G. Van Hameren, D.B. Clarke, J. P. Dreier, D.O. Okonkwo, A. Friedman, Memantine inhibits cortical spreading depolarization and improves neurovascular function following repetitive traumatic brain injury, Sci. Adv. 9 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.adj2417>.
- [59] L.C. Walker, M. Jucker, The prion principle and Alzheimer's disease, Science 385 (2024) 1278–1279, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.adq5252>.
- [60] K. Ito, T. Tatebe, K. Suzuki, T. Hirayama, M. Hayakawa, H. Kubo, T. Tomita, M. Makino, Memantine reduces the production of amyloid- β peptides through modulation of amyloid precursor protein trafficking, Eur. J. Pharmacol. 798 (2017) 16–25, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejphar.2017.02.001>.
- [61] K. Takahashi-Ito, M. Makino, K. Okado, T. Tomita, Memantine inhibits β -amyloid aggregation and disassembles preformed β -amyloid aggregates, Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun. 493 (2017) 158–163, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2017.09.058>.
- [62] S.V.R. Jonnalagadda, A.J. Gerace, K. Thai, J. Johnson, K. Tsimenidis, J. M. Jakubowski, C. Shen, K.J. Henderson, P. Tamamis, M. Grikas, Amyloid peptide scaffolds coordinate with Alzheimer's disease drugs, J. Phys. Chem. B 124 (2020) 487–503, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.9b10368>.
- [63] Y. Inoue, M. Ueda, T. Masuda, Y. Misumi, T. Yamashita, Y. Ando, Memantine, a noncompetitive N-methyl-D-aspartate receptor antagonist, attenuates cerebral amyloid angiopathy by increasing insulin-degrading enzyme expression, Mol. Neurobiol. 56 (2019) 8573–8588, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12035-019-01678-7>.
- [64] S.E. Coombs, S. Banjade, K. Kriksunov, N. Clemente, J. Zhao, C. Wang, R. E. Gillilan, R.E. Oswald, In vitro effects of (+)MK-801 (dizocilpine) and memantine on β -amyloid peptides linked to Alzheimer's disease, Biochemistry 59 (2020) 4517–4522, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.biochem.0c00813>.
- [65] G. Fani, B. Mannini, G. Vecchi, R. Cascella, C. Cecchi, C.M. Dobson, M. Vendruscolo, F. Chiti, A β oligomers dysregulate calcium homeostasis by mechanosensitive activation of AMPA and NMDA receptors, ACS Chem. Neurosci. 12 (2021) 766–781, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.0c00811>.
- [66] K. Bovis, M. Davies-Branch, P.J.R. Day, Dysregulated neurotransmission and the role of viruses in Alzheimer's disease, ACS Chem. Neurosci. 16 (2025) 982–987, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.4c00763>.
- [67] A.A. Spasov, T.V. Khamidova, L.I. Bugaeva, I.S. Morozov, Molecular-biological problems of drug design and mechanism of drug action. Adamantane derivatives: pharmacological and toxicological properties, Pharm. Chem. J. 34 (2000) 3–9, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02524549> (review).
- [68] C. Pathak, U.D. Kabra, A comprehensive review of multi-target directed ligands in the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, Bioorg. Chem. 144 (2024) 107152, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2024.107152>.
- [69] M.M. Koola, A. Nikiforuk, A. Pillai, A.K. Parsaik, Galantamine-memantine combination superior to donepezil-memantine combination in Alzheimer's

- disease: critical dissection with an emphasis on kynurenic acid and mismatch negativity, *J. Geriatr. Care Res.* 5 (2018) 57–67.
- [70] C. Akkaya, S.S. Yavuzer, H. Yavuzer, G. Erkol, M. Bozluolcay, Y. Dincer, DNA damage, DNA susceptibility to oxidation and glutathione redox status in patients with Alzheimer's disease treated with and without memantine, *J. Neurol. Sci.* 378 (2017) 158–162, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jns.2017.04.051>.
- [71] E. Yaghmaei, H. Lu, L. Ehwerhemuepha, J. Zheng, S. Danioko, A. Rezaie, S. A. Sajjadi, C. Rakovski, Combined use of donepezil and memantine increases the probability of five-year survival of Alzheimer's disease patients, *Commun. Med.* 4 (2024) 99, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43856-024-00527-6>.
- [72] R. Chen, P.-T. Chan, H. Chu, Y.-C. Lin, P.-C. Chang, C.-Y. Chen, K.-R. Chou, Treatment effects between monotherapy of donepezil versus combination with memantine for Alzheimer's disease, *PLoS One* 12 (2017) e0183586, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0183586>.
- [73] N. Mittapelly, G. Pandley, S.L. Tulsankar, S. Arfi, R.S. Bhatta, P.R. Mishra, In depth analysis of pressure-sensitive adhesive patch-assisted delivery of memantine and donepezil using physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling and in vitro/in vivo correlations, *Mol. Pharm.* 15 (2018) 2646–2655, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.8b00176>.
- [74] A. Kaur, K. Nigam, S. Srivastava, A. Tyagi, S. Dang, Memantine nanoemulsion: a new approach to treat Alzheimer's disease, *J. Microencapsul.* 37 (2020) 355–365, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652048.2020.1756971>.
- [75] R.R. Radwan, A.M.A. Ghaffar, H.E. Ali, Gamma radiation preparation of chitosan nanoparticles for controlled delivery of memantine, *J. Biomater. Appl.* 34 (2020) 1150–1162, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0885328219890071>.
- [76] P.J. Vos, N. Kuijt, M. Kaya, S. Rol, K. Van der Maaden, Nanoporous microneedle arrays seamlessly connected to a drug reservoir for tunable transdermal delivery of memantine, *Eur. J. Pharmaceut. Sci.* 150 (2020) 105331, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2020.105331>.
- [77] S. Pathuru, G.B. Sankar, G.S. Valluri, C. Raghunadha, *Manufacture and Preparation of Stabilized Combined Multistage Compositions of Memantine HCl Extended Release and Donepezil HCl Immediate Release Pellets*, 2021. Patent WO2021 234475 A1.
- [78] M. Handa, S.N. Sanap, R.S. Bhatta, G.P. Patil, R. Palkhade, D.P. Singh, R. Shukla, Simultaneous intranasal codelivery of donepezil and memantine in a nanocolloidal carrier: optimization, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics studies, *Mol. Pharm.* 20 (2023) 4714–4728, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.3c00454>.
- [79] D. Lee, A.M. Shen, M. Shah, O.B. Garbuzenko, T. Minko, In vivo evaluation of nose-to-brain delivery of liposomal donepezil, memantine, and BACE-1 siRNA for Alzheimer's disease therapy, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 25 (2024) 10357, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms251910357>.
- [80] M.A. Saleh, J.M.M. Mohamed, J.J. Ruby, S. Kanthiah, Y.F. Alanazi, K.A. Mairashi, S.M. Alshahrani, M.A. Eladl, F.S. Alaryani, M. El-Sherbiny, F. Menaa, Preparation of memantine-loaded chitosan nanocrystals: in vitro and ex vivo toxicity analysis, *Crystals* 13 (2023) 21, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst13010021>.
- [81] R. Kanasty, S. Low, N. Bhise, J. Yang, E. Peeke, M. Schwarz, J. Wright, B. Carter, S. Moorthy, T. Grant, B. DeBenedictis, M. Bishoff, C. Simses, A.M. Bellinger, A pharmaceutical answer to nonadherence: once weekly oral memantine for Alzheimer's disease, *J. Contr. Release* 303 (2019) 34–41, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2019.03.022>.
- [82] E. Sánchez-López, M. Etcheto, M.A. Egea, M. Espina, A. Cano, A.C. Calpena, A. Camins, N. Carmona, A.M. Silva, E.B. Souto, M.L. Garcia, Memantine loaded PLGA PEGylated nanoparticles for Alzheimer's disease: in vitro and in vivo characterization, *J. Nanobiotechnol.* 16 (2018) 32, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12951-018-0356-z>.
- [83] G. Tezel, S. Uluturk, T. Recher, S.S. Timur, E. Nemutlu, G. Esendagli, S.G. Pinar, H. Eroglu, Preparation and in vitro characterization of memantine HCl loaded PLGA nanoparticles for Alzheimer's disease, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol.* 100 (2024) 106142, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jddst.2024.106142>.
- [84] O. Antonoglou, K. Giannousi, S. Mourdikoudis, C. Dendrinou-Samara, Magnetic nanoemulsions as candidates for Alzheimer's disease dual imaging theranostics, *Nanotechnology* 31 (2020) 465702, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/abac35>.
- [85] M. Humbert, S. Cohen-Kaminsky, S. Dumas, G. Bru-Mercier, M. Alami, J.-D. Brion, S. Meassaoudi, G. Galvani, Novel Adamantane and Memantine Derivatives as Peripheral NMDA Receptor Antagonists and their Preparation. Patent WO2017 017116 A1, 2017.
- [86] Z. Gazova, O. Soukup, V. Sepsova, K. Sipošova, L. Drtinova, P. Jost, K. Spilovska, J. Korabecny, E. Nepovimova, D. Fedunova, M. Horak, M. Kaniakova, Z.-J. Wang, A.K. Hamouda, K. Kuca, Multi-target-directed therapeutic potential of 7-methoxyacrine-adamantylamine heterodimers in the Alzheimer's disease treatment, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1863 (2017) 607–619, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbadis.2016.11.020>.
- [87] F. Basagni, J.A. Ortega, S.M. Bertozzi, A. Armirotti, M. Summa, R. Bertorelli, M. Bartolini, I.R. Mellor, M. Bedeschi, G. Bottegoni, V. Lembo, A. Minarini, A. Cavalli, M. Rosini, Galantamine-memantine hybrids for Alzheimer's disease: the influence of linker rigidity in biological activity and pharmacokinetic properties, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 261 (2023) 115803, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2023.115803>.
- [88] M. Singhal, V. Merino, M. Rosini, A. Cavalli, Y.N. Kalia, Controlled iontophoretic delivery in vitro and in vivo of ARN14140 – a multitarget compound for Alzheimer's disease, *Mol. Pharm.* 16 (2019) 3460–3468, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.9b00252>.
- [89] T. Kumamoto, M. Nakajima, R. Uga, N. Ihayazaka, H. Kashihara, K. Katakawa, T. Ishikawa, R. Saiki, K. Nishimura, K. Igarashi, Design, synthesis, and evaluation of polyamine-memantine hybrids as NMDA channel blockers, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* 26 (2018) 603–608, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2017.12.021>.
- [90] H. Takayama, Y. Yaegashi, M. Kitajima, X. Han, K. Nishimura, S. Okuyama, K. Igarashi, Design, synthesis, and biological evaluation of tricyclic heterocycle-tetraamine conjugates as potent NMDA channel blockers, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 17 (2007) 4729–4732, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2007.06.069>.
- [91] M.S. Rada, W. Cardona-Galeano, J. Quintero-Saumeth, K. Sierra, E. Osorio, L. A. González-Molina, R. Posada-Duque, A.F. Yepes, Novel multipotent amantadine-M30D hybrids with highly selective butyrylcholinesterase inhibition and neuroprotective effects as effective anti-Alzheimer's agents, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 13 (2022) 2681–2698, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.2c00300>.
- [92] T. Naki, W.M.R. Matshe, M.O. Balogun, S.S. Ray, S.A. Egieyeh, B.A. Aderibigbe, Polymer drug conjugates containing memantine, tacrine and cinchamic acid: promising nanotherapeutics for the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, *J. Microencapsul.* 40 (2023) 15–28, <https://doi.org/10.1080/02652048.2023.2167011>.
- [93] A.P. Araujo de Oliveira, V.C.R. Colmenares, R. Diniz, J.T.J. Freitas, C.M. Da Cruz, E.B. Lages, L.A.M. Ferreira, R.P. Vieira, H. Beraldo, Memantine-derived Schiff bases as transdermal prodrug candidates, *ACS Omega* 7 (2022) 11678–11687, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsomega.1c06571>.
- [94] W. Kuang, J. Liu, X. Lin, S. Wu, J. Gong, Q. Yin, J. Wang, Insoluble salt of memantine with a unique fluorescence phenomenon, *Mol. Pharm.* 19 (2022) 1389–1399, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.1c00931>.
- [95] W. Zhang, N. Kandel, Y. Zhou, N. Smith, B.C.L.B. Ferreira, M. Pérez, M.L. Claire, K.J. Mintz, C. Wang, R.M. Leblanc, Drug delivery of memantine with carbon dots for Alzheimer's disease: blood-brain barrier penetration and inhibition of tau aggregation, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 617 (2022) 20–31, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2022.02.124>.
- [96] G. Sagar, B. Wilson, G.K. Mukundan, K. Divekar, J.L. Jenita, Nanomedicine for treating major brain diseases: advances and future directions, *Mol. Pharm.* 22 (2025) 4413–4434, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.molpharmaceut.5c00277>.
- [97] Z. Li, Z. Zhang, B. Yu, Unlocking the therapeutic potential of natural products for Alzheimer's disease, *J. Med. Chem.* 68 (2025) 2377–2402, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jmedchem.4c03049>.
- [98] K. Pandya, K. Roul, A. Tripathi, S. Belemkar, A. Sinha, M. Erol, D. Kumar, Alzheimer's disease: a review of molecular mechanisms and therapeutic implications by targeting sirtuins, caspases, and CSK-3, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 16 (2025) 2178–2195, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.5c00207>.
- [99] I. Cacciatore, E. Fornasari, L. Marinelli, P. Eusepi, M. Ciulia, O. Ozdemir, A. Tatar, H. Turkez, A. Di Stefano, Memantine-derived drugs as potential antitumor agents for the treatment of glioblastoma, *Eur. J. Pharmaceut. Sci.* 109 (2017) 402–411, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2017.08.030>.
- [100] C. Ning, L. Mo, X. Chen, W. Tu, J. Wu, S. Hou, J. Xu, Triptolide derivatives as potential anti-Alzheimer agents: synthesis and structure-activity relationship studies, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.* 28 (2018) 689–693, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2018.01.019>.
- [101] M. Rosini, E. Simoni, R. Caporaso, F. Basagni, M. Catanzaro, I.F. Abu, F. Fagiani, F. Fusco, S. Masuzzo, D. Albani, C. Lanni, I.R. Mellor, A. Minarini, Merging memantine and ferulic acid to probe connections between NMDA receptors, oxidative stress and amyloid- β peptide in Alzheimer's disease, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 180 (2019) 111–120, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2019.07.011>.
- [102] A. Tencheva, R. Liu, T.V. Volkova, R. Chayrov, Y. Mitrev, M. Štícha, Y. Li, H. Jiang, Z. Li, I. Stankova, G.L. Perlovich, Synthetic analogs of memantine as neuroprotective and influenza viral inhibitors: in vitro and physicochemical studies, *Amino Acids* 52 (2020) 1559–1580, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00726-020-02914-4>.
- [103] R. Chayrov, T. Volkova, G. Perlovich, L. Zeng, Z. Li, M. Štícha, R. Liu, I. Stankova, Synthesis, neuroprotective effect and physicochemical studies of novel peptide and nootropic analogues of Alzheimer disease drug, *Pharmaceuticals* 15 (2022) 1108, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ph15091108>.
- [104] V.B. Sokolov, A.Y. Aksinenko, T.V. Goreva, T.A. Epishina, V.V. Grigor'ev, A. V. Gabrel'yan, D.V. Vinogradova, M.E. Neganova, E.F. Shevtsova, S.O. Bachurin, Molecular design of multitarget neuroprotector 3. Synthesis and bioactivity of tetrahydrocarbazole-aminoadamantane conjugates, *Russ. Chem. Bull.* 65 (2016) 1354–1359, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11172-016-1461-5>.
- [105] P. Sozio, L.S. Cerasa, S. Laserra, I. Cacciatore, C. Cornacchia, E.S. Di Filippo, S. Fulle, A. Fontana, A. Di Crescenzo, M. Grilli, M. Marchi, A. Di Stefano, Memantine-sulfur containing antioxidant conjugates as potential prodrugs to improve the treatment of Alzheimer's disease, *Eur. J. Pharmaceut. Sci.* 49 (2013) 187–198, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejps.2013.02.013>.
- [106] K. Terpstra, C. Gutiérrez, K. Gui, L.M. Mirica, Donepezil and memantine derivatives for dual-function and prodrug applications in Alzheimer's disease, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 16 (2025) 3591–3602, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acscchemneuro.5c00493>.
- [107] B.K. Chen, G. Le Pen, A. Eckmier, G. Rubinstein, T.M. Jay, C.A. Denny, Fluoroethylnormemantine, a novel derivative of memantine facilitates extinction learning without sensorimotor deficits, *Int. J. Neuropharmacol.* 24 (2021) 519–531, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijnp/pyab007>.
- [108] A. Freysson, A. Carles, S. Guehairia, G. Rubinstein, T. Maurice, Fluoroethylnormemantine (FENM) shows synergistic protection in combination with a sigma-1 receptor agonist in a mouse model of Alzheimer's disease, *Neuropharmacology* 242 (2024) 109733, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuropharm.2023.109733>.
- [109] A. Carles, A. Freysson, S. Guehairia, T. Reguero, M. Vignes, H. Hirbec, G. Rubinstein, T. Maurice, Neuroprotection by chronic administration of

- fluoroethylnormemantine (FENM) in mouse models of Alzheimer's disease, *Alzh. Res. Therapy* 17 (2025) 7, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13195-024-01648-9>.
- [110] A.L. Turcu, J. Companys-Aleman, M.B. Phillips, D.S. Patel, C. Grinán-Ferré, M. I. Loza, J.M. Brea, B. Pérez, D. Soto, F.X. Sureda, M.G. Kurnikova, J.W. Johnson, M. Pallàs, S. Vázquez, Design, synthesis, and *in vitro* and *in vivo* characterization of new memantine analogs for Alzheimer's disease, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 236 (2022) 114354, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2022.114354>.
- [111] Y. Wu, V. Pons, R. Noël, S. Kali, O. Shtanko, R.A. Davey, M.R. Popoff, N. Tordo, D. Gillet, J.-C. Cintrat, J. Barbier, DABMA: a derivative of ABMA with improved broad-spectrum inhibitory activity of toxins and viruses, *ACS Med. Chem. Lett.* 10 (2019) 1140–1147, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmchemlett.9b00155>.
- [112] S. Sestito, S. Daniele, D. Pietrobono, V. Citi, L. Bellusci, G. Chiellini, V. Calderone, C. Martini, S. Rapposelli, Memantine prodrug as a new agent for Alzheimer's disease, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (2019) 4612, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-40925-8>.
- [113] Z. Liu, S. Yang, X. Jin, G. Zhang, B. Guo, H. Chen, P. Yu, Y. Sun, Z. Zhang, Y. Wang, Synthesis and biological evaluation of memantine nitrates as a potential treatment for neurodegenerative diseases, *Medchemcomm* 8 (2016) 135–147, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6md00509h>.
- [114] S. Mak, Z. Liu, L. Wu, B. Guo, F. Luo, Z. Liu, S. Hu, J. Wang, G. Cui, Y. Sun, Y. Wang, G. Zhang, Y. Han, Z. Zhang, Pharmacological characterization of anti-dementia memantine nitrate via neuroprotection and vasodilation *in vitro* and *in vivo*, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 11 (2020) 314–327, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acchemneuro.9b00242>.
- [115] M.A. Altinoz, I. Elmaci, Targeting nitric oxide and NMDA receptor-associated pathways in treatment of high grade glial tumors. Hypotheses for nitro-memantine and nitrones, *Nitric Oxide* 79 (2018) 68–83, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.niox.2017.10.001>.
- [116] T. Nakamura, S.A. Lipton, Preventing Ca²⁺-mediated nitrosative stress in neurodegenerative diseases: possible pharmacological strategies, *Cell Calcium* 47 (2010) 190–197, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ceca.2009.12.009>.
- [117] S.J. Thomas, G.T. Grossberg, Memantine: a review of studies into its safety and efficacy in treating Alzheimer's disease and other dementias, *Clin. Interv. Aging* 4 (2009) 367–377, <https://doi.org/10.2147/cia.s6666>.
- [118] K. Czarnecka, J. Chuchmacz, P. Wójtowicz, P. Szymanski, Memantine in neurological disorders – schizophrenia and depression, *J. Mol. Med.* 99 (2021) 327–334, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00109-020-01982-z>.
- [119] S.E. Hoss, H. Bazoum, From old to new: repurposed drugs in the battle towards curing sickle cell disease, *Br. J. Haematol.* 206 (2025) 795–797, <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjh.19912>.
- [120] H. Hu, L. Wu, X. Hu, M. Wang, Y. Sun, G. Zhang, Y. Wang, P. Yi, Z. Zhang, Neuroprotective and intraocular pressure lowering effects of dual-functional memantine nitrate MN-08 on the experimental models of glaucoma, *Sci. Rep.* 15 (2025) 23822, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-06832-x>.
- [121] R.H. Mohyeldin, E.E. Sharata, M.A. Fawzy, M.E. Attya, N.N. Welson, R.R. Rofaeil, Memantine abrogates testicular dysfunction induced by risperidone in rats with a potential role of ERK1/2-Nrf2-caspase-3 signaling pathway, *Sci. Rep.* 15 (2025) 12914, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-94760-1>.
- [122] S. Pal, et al., Safety and efficacy of memantine and trazodone versus placebo for motor neuron disease (MND SMART): stage two interim analysis from the first cycle of a phase 3, multiarm, multistage, randomized, adaptive platform trial, *Lancet Neurol.* 23 (2024) 1097–1107, [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1474-4422\(24\)00326-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1474-4422(24)00326-0).
- [123] D.F. Weaver, Alzheimer's is not a single disease, *ACS Chem. Neurosci.* 16 (2025) 2340–2342, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acchemneuro.5c00446>.
- [124] M.E. Pizzo, et al., Transferrin receptor-targeted anti-amyloid antibody enhances brain delivery and mitigates ARIA, *Science* 389 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.ads3204> eads3204.
- [125] L. Aron, Z.K. Ngian, C. Qiu, J. Choi, M. Liang, D.M. Drake, S.E. Hamplova, E. K. Lacey, P. Roche, M. Yuan, S.S. Hazaveh, E.A. Lee, D.A. Bennett, B.A. Yankner, Lithium deficiency and the onset of Alzheimer's disease, *Nature* 645 (2025) 712–721, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-025-09335-x>.
- [126] H.L. Leonard, M.A. Nalls, A. Day-Williams, S. Esmaeeli, P. Jarreau, S. Bandres-Ciga, P. Heutink, S.P. Sardi, A.B. Singleton, Open science in precision medicine for neurodegenerative diseases, *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* 23 (2024) 233–234, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41573-024-00017-3>.
- [127] A. Shvetcov, E.C.B. Johnson, L.M. Winchester, K.A. Walker, H.M. Wilkins, T. G. Thompson, J.D. Rothstein, V. Krish, F.B. Imam, , The Global Neurodegeneration Proteomics Consortium (GNPC), J.M. Burns, R.H. Swerdlow, C. Slawson, C.A. Finney, *APOE ε4* carries share immune-related proteomic changes across neurodegenerative diseases, *Nat. Med.* 31 (2025) 2590–2601, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-025-03835-z>.